

SITE GPR	YEAR 2011	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.550 Max: 62.649	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1437 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	Gator Project

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 19/2, 13 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Fill of cut west of 1403
 Covered by: SU: 1407 Fills: SU: 1438 Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery (m) <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) (r) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay (r) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sand (m) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt (f) <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones (r) <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth (r) <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 5% silt 80% sand 15% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: SU 1427	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: SU 1438

OBSERVATIONS: The cut emerges from the bulk of our excavation limit, only southern section excavated. 33cm wide, 42cm deep. - Depth may not be original, as the cut may have originated at a higher level.

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: South-central Area B 2011, between house + quarry debris
 Shape: Rectangular

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): —
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): —
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): —
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Fill that may be related to a grave given its shape, and the fact that only 30 centimeters have been excavated, given the excavation limit.

May relate to post hole, as there are large rocks below. The fill is somewhat similar to the subounding material, making identification difficult.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	J. FARR C. Bennett	on	25.7.2011
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